

THE REDOX POTENTIAL OF LACTATE-PYRUVATE SYSTEM.

BY S. C. GANGULI.

The lactate-pyruvate system is directly involved in the carbohydrate metabolism of living systems. Consequently it has been the subject of study of many authors. Its redox potential has been measured by Barron and Hastings (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 107, 567), Banga, Laki, and Szent-Gyorgyi (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1933, 217, 43), Wurmser and Myer-Reich (*J. chim. phys.*, 1933, 30, 429) and Baumberger, Jurgensen, and Bardwell (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1933, 16, 961). These authors have shown that in presence of suitable enzymes and electromotive activators this system behaves reversibly and a stable electrode potential is obtained at an inert electrode. The electrode reaction is given by the equation :—

and the electrode potential is given by

$$E_p = \bar{E} - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{(\text{lactate}')} {(\text{pyruvate}')} - \frac{RT}{F} p_{\text{H}^+} - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left\{ \frac{K_p}{K_l} \times \frac{K_l + (\text{H}^+)}{K_p + (\text{H}^+)} \right\}$$

where K_p and K_l are the dissociation constants of pyruvic acid and lactic acid respectively. K_p is 3.2×10^{-3} and K_l is 1.55×10^{-4} . ' \bar{E} ' is the Borsook normal potential which is related with Clark normal potential E_0 by the relationship,

$$E_0 = \bar{E} + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{K_p}{K_l}.$$

The value of E_0 found by Banga (*et al*), Wurmser (*et al*) and Barron and Hastings is + 0.288 volts, whereas Baumberger and co-workers have found $E_0 = + 0.316$ volts.

All the above investigations were complicated by the facts that :—
(a) some enzymes were introduced in the system whose behaviour towards electrodes is not very clearly known, (b) some dyestuffs were introduced. Barron and Hastings in order to account for the discrepancy state that "The discrepancy between the values given by Baumberger, Jurgensen and Bardwell for the normal potential of the system under consideration

(+ 0.316 volts) and the concordant values obtained by Wurmser and Meyer-Reich, Banga, Laki, and Szent-Gyorgyi, and ourselves is probably due to the use of a dye as the electroactive mediator of too positive a potential, compared with the potential of lactate-pyruvate." It was thought by the present author that if the potential of the lactate-pyruvate system could be measured without the introduction of these complicating factors, then a choice could be made between these two values.

The electro-reduction method described by Ghosh, Raychaudhuri, and Ganguli (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 43), was considered suitable for the end in view. Pyruvic acid was partially reduced electrolytically in absence of oxygen at a mercury or platinum cathode and the potential of the polarised electrode was measured from time to time against a *N/10* calomel electrode. After 6-8 hours a limiting potential was obtained which was steady for more than $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was found that this limiting potential could be expressed by the usual thermodynamic formula. The value of E_0 obtained was + 0.325 volts at 30°, rather higher than the value obtained by any of the previous authors. Measurements were made both at mercury and platinum electrodes. But whereas the reduction of pyruvate to lactate took place at a Hg-cathode smoothly between p_H 6.47 and p_H 8.38, pyruvic acid could not be reduced to lactic acid at a Pt-cathode above p_H 7.9. At Hg surface also no readings could be taken above p_H 8.38, the electrolytic reduction product not being pure lactic acid above that p_H .

The experimental arrangement was similar to that described by Ghosh, Raychaudhuri and Ganguli (*loc. cit.*) with the following modifications:—

(a) The pyrogallic acid tower in the nitrogen purification train was omitted.

(b) All glass to glass connections were made with impregnated pressure tube coated outside with vacuum grease. This was found to be as satisfactory as ground-glass joints.

(c) In place of the siphon tube and the KCl tube, two agar KCl bridges were used.

In order to prevent the oxidation of pyruvic acid in alkaline solution the following procedure was adopted:—A known volume of buffer solution was introduced in the electrolytic vessel, the stopper put in position and the vessel was de-aerated by a stream of nitrogen, and known amount of pyruvic acid was then introduced through the stop-cock. A pyruvic acid solution of the same concentration and p_H was used as the anolyte. The reduction current was then switched on, the current density being 10^{-4} ampere per sq. cm. Platinum cathodes, when used, were 2 cm. sq. The

total lactic and pyruvic acid content of the final solution was estimated in a portion of the solution by the iodoform method. This was necessary in order to ensure that the sum of these two acids represented all the pyruvic acid that was originally added. Pyruvic acid was estimated in another portion of the solution by the colorimetric method of Case (*Biochem J.*, 1932 **26**, 753). Lactic acid was obtained by difference.

Kahlbaum's pyruvic acid, freshly distilled in vacuum, was used. The system is more susceptible to traces of oxygen than the cystine-cysteine system. A slow current of nitrogen was kept passing through the vessel throughout the experiment. The equilibrium was always approached from the same side. With proper precautions it was possible to reproduce the results to within ± 5 mv.

TABLE I.
Readings with Hg-cathode.

pH .	Total conc.	Oxd./Red.	E_h .	E_o .
6.47	0.0132M	0.40/0.65	-0.064 volts.	+0.330
6.97	"	0.750/0.320	-0.0793	+0.328
7.15	"	1.560/0.430	-0.0865	+0.325
7.25	"	0.356/1.680	-0.119	+0.335
7.72	0.01256	1.515/0.395	-0.120	+0.326
7.89	"	0.590/0.230	-0.136	+0.324
7.89	"	0.475/1.435	-0.163	+0.324
8.15	"	0.695/0.312	-0.159	+0.319
8.36	0.01332	0.685/0.395	-0.159	+0.335
8.38	"	0.161/0.904	-0.199	+0.326
				Mean + 0.327

TABLE II.
Readings with the platinum electrodes.

pH .	Total conc.	Oxd./Red.	E_h .	E_o .
6.86	0.01256M	10.0/1.0	-0.054	+0.327
6.23	0.01332	1.200/0.460	-0.038	+0.323

It was not possible to reduce pyruvic acid at a Pt-cathode above p_H 7.0. Below p_H 7.0 the reduction is also never complete, but lower the p_H , the higher is the percentage of reduction.

That the system lactate \rightleftharpoons pyruvate should be able to maintain a stable potential at an inert electrode is rather strange. The work of Conant and Cutter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1016) has provided that unlike the reduction of double bonded compounds, the reduction of pyruvate to lactate is not the simple addition of two hydrogen atoms to the molecule but involves the change of two electronic charges as well. Probably when a film of oxygen or oxide is present on the metal surface this type of electron change is not able to charge a noble metal electrode. Ghosh and Ganguli (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 381) have shown that the sulphhydryl system becomes reversively active only when the oxygen film is removed. The lactate-pyruvate system may be another type of system which shows no electron activity at all in presence of the film.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BENGAL ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
SHIBPUR, HOWRAH.

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